

COcyber – Coordination Between the Cybersecurity Civilian And Defence Spheres

Joining Forces for Digital Safety in Europe

The European cybersecurity sector faces expanding challenges that require **more cooperation**, **improved information** sharing, and **skilled professionals** to respond effectively. In COcyber, we aim to tackle these evolving threats by linking civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres.

Our Mission – Building a Robust and Inclusive Cybersecurity Ecosystem in Europe

Through trusted infrastructures, we help strengthen cooperation and ensure Europe's strategic autonomy.

Knowledge

A forum for the exchange of expertise and information on cybersecurity.

Harmonisation

Policy recommendations for harmonising European actions.

Tools

A set of concrete instruments for engagement, collaboration and information sharing.

Synergies

A vibrant European community of cybersecurity stakeholders.

Bridging Civilian and Defence Cybersecurity Sectors

COcyber brings together civilian and defence cybersecurity stakeholders through activities, events, and collaborations. **Join us in the COcyber community now!**

20+ active collaborations	10+ high-level tech roundtables	4+ cybersecurity consultations	10+ capacity-building activities
8+ policy-oriented workshops	4+ research and innovation seminars	10+ identified best practices	

Meet the COcyber Team

- Coordination and Support Action running for 2 years, until June 2026.
- Implemented by a multidisciplinary team of 9 European partners.
- 2.97 M€ of budget funded by the European Union, with the European Cybersecurity Center as the grant authority.

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